

STUDIES IN CELLULOSE ACETATE. PART III.

BY PIJUSH KANTI CHOUDHURY

Identical results as reported in Part II of this paper have been obtained by using different proportions of cellulose and acetylating mixtures.

In Part II of this series (*This Journal*, 1947, 24, 271) the author gave results of acetylation where a certain proportion of cellulose and acetylating mixture, namely C : Ac : An = 1 : 5 : 4 (C = cellulose, Ac = glacial acetic acid, An = acetic anhydride) was always maintained. The only variable was the percentage of H₂SO₄ used as a catalyst, the reaction temperature being the same in all the experiments undertaken. Practically identical results were obtained using different percentages of H₂SO₄ as catalyst, maintaining the same proportion of cellulose and acetylating mixture.

Further investigations reveal that identical results can be obtained even by using different proportions of cellulose and acetylating mixture, as will be evident from the tables given below. The abbreviations used signifying the degree of solubility are the same as used in Part II (*loc. cit.*). S = soluble; I. S. = insoluble; L. S. = less soluble; M. S. = moderately soluble; P. S. = partly soluble; C. S. = completely soluble; P = plastic.

TABLE I

Expt. No. 7. Cellulose : acetic acid : acetic anhydride = 1 : 5 : 3. Catalyst = 12.9% H₂SO₄.

No. of sample.	Duration of reaction (total hrs.)	*Period of hydrolysis (total hrs.)	Solubility at room temp. in		Acetic acid content.
			Chloroform.	Acetone.	
1.	0.0	x	M. S.	Swelling	62.4%
2.	8.0	x	S.	P. S.	61.2
3.	24.0	x	C. S.	C. S.	59.8
4.	27.0	2	"	"	58.4
5.	30.0	5	L. S.	"	56.2
6.	32.0	7	P.	"	54.0
7.	48.5	23.5	I. S.	"	48.6
8.	52.0	27.0	"	S. but not easily	49.0
9.	55.0	30.0	"	L. S.	47.4

Expt. No. 8. C : Ac : An = 1 : 4 : 4. Catalyst = 12.9% H₂SO₄.

1.	6.0	x	M. S.	I. S.	61.6
2.	8.0	x	S.	P. S.	61.2
3.	24.0	x	C. S.	C. S.	59.7
4.	27.0	2.5	L. S.	"	56.2
5.	30.0	5.5	P.	"	54.6
6.	32.0	7.5	P.	"	54.0
7.	48.0	23.5	I. S.	S.	48.7
8.	55.0	30.5	"	I. S.	46.8

Expt. No. 9. C : Ac : An = 1 : 5 : 4. Catalyst = 18.4% H₂SO₄.

1.	4	x	S. but not easily	I. S.	62.4
2.	6	x	M. S.	"	61.8
3.	8	x	S.	P. S.	61.2
4.	10	x	C. S.	S.	60.6
5.	12	x	"	C. S.	60.0
6.	24	x	"	"	59.8
7.	26	2	"	"	59.2
8.	28	4	"	"	57.6
9.	30	6	L. S.	"	55.1
10.	32	8	P.	"	54.0
11.	34	10	I. S.	"	52.7

* after the addition of 65% acid

TABLE II

No. of sample,	Duration of reaction (total hrs.)	*Period of hydrolysis (total hrs.)	Solubility at room temperature in		Acetic acid content.
			Chloroform.	Acetone.	
Expt. No. 7. C : Ac : An = 1 : 5 : 3. Catalyst = 12.9% H ₂ SO ₄ .					
3.	24	x	O.S.	C.S.	58.8%
4.	28	4	"	"	57.6
5.	32	9	P.	"	54.0
6.	48	24.5	I.S.	"	49.6
7.	55	31.0	"	"	47.2
Expt. No. 8. C : Ac : An = 1 : 4 : 4. Catalyst = 12.9% H ₂ SO ₄ .					
3.	24	x	C.S.	C.S.	58.8
4.	28	4	L.S.	"	55.8
5.	32	8	P.	"	54.0
6.	48	24	I.S.	"	49.7
7.	55	31	"	L.S.	47.3
Expt. No. 9. C : Ac : An = 1 : 5 : 4. Catalyst = 18.4% H ₂ SO ₄ .					
6.	24	x	C.S.	C.S.	58.8
7.	28	2	"	"	58.2
8.	28	4	S.	"	57.6
9.	30	6	L.S.	"	56.4
10.	32	8	P.	"	54.4
11.	34	10	I.S.	"	52.7

* Without the addition of 65% acid or water.

TABLE III

No. of sample,	Duration of the reaction (total hrs.)	*Period of hydrolysis (total hrs.)	Solubility at room temperature in		Acetic acid content.
			Chloroform.	Acetone.	
Expt. No. 9. C : Ac : An = 1 : 5 : 4. Catalyst = 12.9% H ₂ SO ₄ .					
1.	4	x	S. but not easily	I.S.	62.4%
2.	6	x	M.S.	"	61.8
3.	23	2	C.S.	C.S.	57.0
4.	25	2	"	"	56.4
5.	27	4	"	"	55.8
6.	29	6	L.S.	"	55.2
7.	31	8	P.	"	53.5

* Without the addition of 65% acid or water. but maintaining at a temperature of 40-45°.

TABLE IV

No. of experiment.	No. of sample.	Period of reversion in hrs. (%)	% of H ₂ SO ₄ used as catalyst.	Ratio of (C : Ac : An)	% Acetic acid content mean expt. value	calc. from formula.	% Diff. between the two.	REMARKS.
6,9,10	1,1,1	4	16.4,18.4,12.9	1 : 5 : 4	62.4	62.4	Nil	
3,4,5,6 7,8,9,11	1,1,1,1 1,1,2,2	0	14.7,16.6,18.4 20.2,12.9,12.9 16.4,12.9	1 : 5 : 4 (for Nos. 3,4,5,6,9,10) 1 : 5 : 3 (for No. 7) 1 : 4 : 4 (for No. 8)	62.1	61.6	+0.5	
3,4,5,6, 7,8,9	2,2,3,3 2,2,3	6	Do.	Do	61.3	61.2	+0.2	
7	4	10	16.4	1 : 5 : 4	60.6	60.6	Nil	In this case the solution was kept overnight at 40-46°.
8	5	12	Do.	Do	60.0	60.0	Nil	
10	3	23	12.9	Do	67.0	66.7	+0.5	
3,5,6,7, 8,9	3,4,3,3, 3,6	24	14.7,16.4,20.2, 12.9,12.9,16.4	1 : 5 : 4 (for Nos. 3,5,6,7) 1 : 5 : 3 (for No. 7) 1 : 4 : 4 (for No. 8)	58.6	59.4	+4.3	As the solution was kept overnight at ordinary temperature (30-32°) instead of 40-46°, the reaction slowed down.
3,10, 3,5,6,	4,4, 5,5,4	25 26	14.7,12.9 14.7,16.4,20.2	1 : 5 : 4 Do	57.6 57.6	56.1 55.6	+2.0 +3.2	
1,2,7 6,10	1,1,4 4,5	27	11.0,12.9,12.9 12.9,12.9	1 : 5 : 4 (for Nos. 1,2 & 10) 1 : 5 : 3 (for No. 7) 1 : 4 : 4 (for No. 8)	55.8	55.5	+0.5	

TABLE IV (continued)

No. of experiment.	No. of sample.	Period of reaction in hrs. (Z).	% of H ₂ SO ₄ used as catalyst.	Ratio of (C : Ac : An)	% Acetic acid content mean expt. value.	calc. from formula.	% Diff. between the two.	REMARKS.
3.5.6.9.	7.6.5.8.	28	14.7, 18.4, 20.2, 18.4.	1 : 5 : 4	55.5	55.2	+0.5	
10.	6	28	12.9	Do	55.2	54.9	+0.5	
3.6.7.8. 9	8.6.5.5. 9	30	14.7, 20.2, 12.9, 18.4.	1 : 5 : 4 (for Nos. 3, 6, 9)				
				1 : 5 : 3, (for No. 7)	54.3	54.6	-0.5	
				1 : 4 : 4 (for No. 8)				
3.5.6.7. 8, 10	9, 7, 6 6, 10, 7.	32	14.7, 18.4, 20.2, 12.9, 12.9, 16.4, 12.9.	1 : 5 : 4 (for Nos. 3, 5, 6, 9, 10) 1 : 5 : 3 (for No. 7) 1 : 4 : 4 (for No. 8)	53.7	54.0	-0.5	
3.5.6.7. 8.	11, 9, 8, 7, 7.	48	14.7, 18.4, 20.2, 12.9, 12.9	1 : 5 : 4 (for Nos. 3, 5, 6) 1 : 5 : 3 (for No. 7) 1 : 4 : 4 (for No. 8)	48.5	49.2	+1.4	
3.6.7.8	12, 9, 9, 8	55	14.7, 20.2, 12.9, 12.9	1 : 5 : 4 (for Nos. 3 & 6) 1 : 5 : 4 (for No. 7) 1 : 4 : 4 (for No. 8)	46.5	47.1	+1.3	

In the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) it was postulated that the hydrolysis of tri-acetates to di-acetates could be brought about without the presence of dilute acetic acid or water, the only difference observed between the one hydrolysed in the usual way and the other hydrolysed without the addition of water, being longer hours, required by the latter to give the same product or products. Further investigations have revealed that if the temperature of 40-45° is maintained throughout the experiment then the longer hours, as postulated to be required by the product hydrolysed without the addition of water, can be so effectively minimized that the hydrolysis may produce the identical lowering down in the percentage content of acetic acid of the acetate. Results shown in Tables I and II justify this postulate.

If the results of these tables, as well as those of the Part II (*loc. cit.*) are scrutinized, it will be observed that the percentage acetic acid content of the acetate bears a definite relation with the period of reaction during and after acetylation. This relation holds good in practically all the results obtained, irrespective of the ratio of cellulose and acetylating mixture as well as that of the percentage of H_2SO_4 used as catalyst. Further observation reveals that the percentage of acetic acid content in between the two definite hours of reaction, say between 4 and 8 hours or 28 and 32 hours, is lowered down by a constant or a multiple of a constant, which has been found to be a figure near about 1.2. This has led the author for the process of acetylation, in all probability, to formulate a simple linear reaction, guided by the following formula,

$$Y = C + 1.2 X \text{ and}$$

$$X = \frac{1}{4}(C + 4 - Z)$$

where Y = % acetic acid content of cellulose acetate,

X = degree of acetylation,

Z = total hours of reaction, and

C = a constant, namely 48, which is the % acetic acid content of a true di-acetate.

Now if Z is known, we can easily find out the value of X and from that Y may be easily evaluated.

The results given in Table IV postulate a very close relation between the percentage acetic acid of an acetate with the period of reaction. This also justifies to a great measure the assumption and validity of the mathematical expression, as proposed. Excepting two cases, namely when the period of reaction is 24 and 26 hours, the difference between the experimental and calculated results is very small, namely 0.5% only, which may be easily overlooked. The bigger differences in the two cases, cited above, may be due, according to the author.

to keeping the solution overnight at ordinary temperature (30-32°) instead of at 40-45°, the optimum temperature of the reaction. This assumption is substantiated by the fact that in the case of reaction period of 23 hours, the difference is only +0.5%. Further, as temperature is gradually raised and kept at 40-45° from 24th hour to 27th, the difference observed is again small, namely 0.5% in the latter cases.

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INDIA OIL PLASTICS LABORATORY,
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CALCUTTA.

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